

Scientific Perspective on Occupational Health and Safety Culture

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Scientific Perspective on Occupational Health and Safety Culture

Abstract

In this article, using a comprehensive examination of occupational health and safety culture literature to describe three basic themes, the role of new employees focuses on the lack of an

initiative-taking approach and the need for an ideal culture. Being investigating the effects of knowledge, theory and assumptions on occupational health and safety culture in a scientific language will contribute to the literature with this article. Although it is the subject of other work, although it is the subject of other work to investigate and examine the information and education of employees, workers and union representatives of the occupational health and security culture, including institutional structures, managers and supervisors in many countries . This study provides pioneering or reference information in terms of emphasizing the importance of these issues at the institutional and individual level. Because, in accordance with the importance of the use of qualitative data with a constructivist phenomenological approach, certain examples are supported by research and compilations in literature studies. Classification according to concepts and expressions, revealing norms derived from their cultural attitudes and beliefs to make a thematic analysis is important for the knowledge, behavior, interest, attitude and practical conferences and practices of employees. The fact that the findings confirm the three themes defined from our literature screening provides useful information about the difficulties faced by the participants in the implementation of security policies. In addition to expanding the occupational health and safety literature, these findings have significant administrative effects for the developing nature of work and workplaces.

Keywords: *Health, Safety Culture, Occupational Health and Safety Culture, Corporate Occupational Health, Occupational Safety, Business Health, and Safety*

1. Introduction

“Safety Culture” is defined as “common attitudes, values, and perceptions towards safety held by organizational groups” that are assumed to be “both the product and driver of risk-related practices” (Teard et al., 2020, p. 550), Cooper, 2000, Zohar, based on the seminal work of 2002 in this field, he makes important determinations. Safety culture represents and operates the psychological and behavioral characteristics of organizations, which can lead to the success or failure of Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) practices (Teared et al., 2020). Safety culture is defined as a critical factor that sets the tone for the recognition of the importance of safety in

an organization (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2007). With the increasing acceptance of safety culture as a key driver of organizational safety outcomes, regulators in different industries have increasingly focused on safety culture in their audits and contacts with companies (Nævestad et al., 2019). (“Toward an effective occupational health and safety culture: A multiple ...”) Therefore, it is not surprising to see increasing efforts to establish an evidence-based approach to develop OHS interventions to address a wide range of safety issues across multiple industries (Cunningham et al., 2020).

2. Health and Safety Management Systems

The incidence of occupational injuries and diseases associated with industrialization has declined markedly following advances in science and technology such as engineering controls, protective equipment, safer machinery and processes, and adherence to regulations and workforce controls. However, the decline in occupational injuries and illnesses is only minimal, which has led to increased interest in health and safety management systems. Although the introduction of these systems has further reduced the incidence of occupational injury and illness, workforce safety and health management systems are not effective in workplaces with a weak safety culture (Hale AR, 1998. pp. 129–166). The International Labor Organization (ILO) has also noted that a key element for occupational safety and health management is fostering a culture of prevention within the enterprise (International Labor Organization (ILO) Office). (“Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...”) The introduction of a positive safety culture can therefore lead to further reductions in occupational injuries and illnesses. When the term “safety culture” first appeared in the literature, the international atomic energy agency introduced the term in its 1986 Chernobyl Accident Summary report to describe how it contributed to the thinking and behavior of people in the organization responsible for nuclear power plant safety (International Nuclear Safety Advisory Group (HSC) International Atomic Energy Agency ; Vienna (Austria): 1986.). In 1993, the Nuclear Installation Safety Advisory Committee (ACSNI) investigated disasters such as the Chernobyl meltdown, the king’s crossfire, the piper alpha explosion, and the train crash at Clapham Junction and concluded that the safety systems at these workplaces had failed. This failure was caused by problems with the “safety culture” of the responsible organizations, not

the safety management method. The lesson learned from these disasters is “needed to create a corporate atmosphere or culture where safety is and is recognized as the number one priority” (Health and Safety Commission (HSC) HSC; London (UK): 1993).

3. “ Safety Culture” and Practices Related to Risks

Although technology and occupational health and safety management systems have made great strides in creating a safer world, the promotion and development of a safety culture in the workplace is key to further improvement. (“Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...”) Legal authorities, higher bodies or councils in many countries promote occupational safety awareness in employers and employees of high-risk transactions to promote a culture of safety in the workplace. It can be said that these organizations also develop a safety culture. Of course, it is promising that employees and consultants on safety culture work with various participants, including workers and union representatives, to the extent that we can use our data for a qualitative study with a constructivist phenomenological approach. It reveals the parallelism of the fixed data in the literature with the functioning of the higher institutions to make a thematic analysis to classify these elements with certain concepts and expressions, and to reveal the cultural norms derived from their attitudes and beliefs. Along with expanding the occupational health and safety literature, these findings have important managerial implications for the evolving nature of work and workplaces. (“Improving workplace safety by thinking about what might ... - ScienceDirect”) Because “Safety Culture” is defined as “common attitudes, values and perceptions towards safety held by organizational groups” which are assumed to be both the product and driver of risk-related practices (Teard et al., 2020, p. 550).

Cooper, 2000, Zohar, 2002 have done many studies in this area. Safety culture represents and operates the psychological and behavioral characteristics of organizations, which can lead to the success or failure of Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) practices (Teared et al., 2020). Safety culture is defined as a critical factor that sets the tone for the recognition of the importance of safety in an organization (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2007). With the increasing acceptance of safety culture as a key driver of organizational safety outcomes, regulators in different industries have increasingly focused on safety culture in their audits and contacts with

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The incidence of occupational injuries and diseases associated with industrialization has declined markedly following advances in science and technology such as engineering controls, protective equipment, safer machinery and processes, and adherence to regulations and workforce controls. However, the decline in occupational injuries and illnesses is only minimal, which has led to increased interest in health and safety management systems . Although the introduction of these systems has further reduced the incidence of occupational injury and illness, workforce safety and health management systems are not effective in workplaces with a weak safety culture. While a range of health, safety, and environmental issues are increasingly on the agenda like never before , these concerns are already affecting how companies operate and interact with the public. (“Sustainability Is the New Safety - JPT”) A pilot program with nine companies, called the SafeOCS industry security database, administered by the U.S. Bureau of Transportation Statistics, has selected three potential next steps for use of this industry-wide security database. (“Frontiers | Assessing the Mediating Role of Safety Communication ...”) One of the main steps is: “To develop effective communication processes, including dashboards, to share lessons learned, review aggregated results, assess causal factors, network and discuss potential actions to prevent recurrence and thereby increase safety” (Collina DV, Moreau RL . SafeOCS industry safety data 2019).

Curlee et al. (Curlee CK, Brouillard SJ, Marshall ML, Knode TL, Smith SL) statistically analyzed the highest mortality rates of all major industries typically including all petrochemical and oil and gas production and exploration activities. Along the same lines, Cloughley and Thomas (Cloughley T, Thomas I. Accident data for the upstream oil and gas industry) noted that this prochemistry tends to be harsh and dangerous as these chemical activities take place in the Ahigh pressure and high temperature (HPHT) environment. Based on the above argument, it is fair to assume that safety communication will mediate the relationship between safety culture and employee safety performance. By reducing accidents, a safety culture allows

employers
their
resources
achieving
improving

to invest

in
and
safety

performance (Aboramadan M, Dahleez KA, 2021).

Figure – 1: Noisy areas and workers with signs of occupational noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL). Number of noisy areas in the workplace from 1992 to 2009 (Yangho Kim, 1, Jungsun Park, and Mijin Park)

4. Global Examples of the Importance of Occupational Health and Safety

It would be appropriate to give examples of research in the context of newly industrialized countries, aiming to provide new theoretical and practical information on the relationship between safety culture and safety performance by investigating the key role of safety communication as a mediating variable. Literature reviews in the field must deal with the instability of the production process. Because it is necessary to understand how this issue is evaluated by the employees whose productivity has decreased due to the lack of occupational safety and culture. For example, activities in the oil or mining sector such as overstable wells, gas leaks, and often the reactive nature of hydrocarbon sources tend to create life-threatening situations if not well monitored (Dawson P. Paul Chapman Publishing, 1994.). We give this example because much of the literature has focused on the health safety environment (HSE) in the petrochemical, oil and gas industry . Again, according to the National Security Council statistics in 2010, it is obvious that employers who pay “1 billion USD per week” for direct personnel compensation costs are not sufficiently informed or trained on this critical issue. The values equal to 80 million days lost each year confirm that the most important issue to be considered economically is the subject of our study (Kanter RM, Stein BA, Jick TD, 1992.). While deaths and injuries are irreversible effects, there are also a few financial and environmental impacts. Indeed, if all institutions and workers behave and perform in a safe manner, production will certainly not increase, or at least not decrease. A survey conducted by

Liberty Mutual and cited by (Kanter RM, Stein BA, Jick TD, 1992.) highlighted the following among managers:

- a. *9% indicated that a company's financial performance was greatly affected by a safe workplace.*
- b. *61% assumed that for every \$1 invested in the security, a return of \$3 or more is observed.*
- c. *13% indicated that for every \$1 invested in security, \$10 will be refunded.*
- d. *and 40% expected indirect costs of \$3 to \$5 for every \$1 in direct injury or incident costs.*

The negative effects of industrial events on social loss have been evaluated in many studies. Many organizations have three sectors:

- i. *upstream,*
- ii. *medium and*
- iii. *downstream.*

Employees in all three sectors operate in high-risk conditions (Figure 1). The upstream sector is responsible for the production of basic raw materials, the midstream sector is for intermediates, and the downstream sector is responsible for the processing and production of various by-products. Despite the beneficial contributions of all these studies, there is relatively little research on the impact of organizational culture on workers' attitudes towards safety, which can be used to ameliorate or intervene in safety issues (Antonsen, 2017). This is especially important for new employees in any organization who, due to a lack of appropriate training or previous experience, cannot share the same knowledge, attitudes, commitments and behaviors as existing employees (O'Kelley, 2019).

However, there is little research on the impact of new employees on an established safety culture. This is especially true for new 'short-term employment' relationships, which may have a major barrier to establishing a workplace culture (Anyfantis & Boustras, 2020). ("Toward an effective occupational health and safety culture: A multiple ...") Similarly, researchers have called for an initiative-taking approach to creating and managing a culture of safety that goes beyond just policies and procedures (for example, Curcuruto et al., 2019, Curcuruto et al., 2020,

Teary et al., 2020). For example, Silla et al. (2017) enables employees to report safety issues without fear, while Zuschlag et al. (2016) discussed continuous security improvements and security paramount issues with feedback as tools to increase the effectiveness of the safety culture. Mackenzie et al. (2019) also highlights worker engagement and participation as key elements of an effective safety culture. Therefore, we need a more initiative-taking approach to improving workplace safety outcomes as an alternative to traditional approaches based mainly on rules and regulations.

Figure – 2: Number of workers in the workplace with definite or probable signs of NIHL from 1992 to 2009. TWA, time-weighted average. (Yangho Kim, Jungsun Park, and Mijin Park)

Researchers also describe 'safety culture' and employee barriers to poor safety practices, which is associated with concepts of lack or absence of knowledge common in many organizations (Walker, 2013) .

Dekker (2009) reinforces this point by arguing that organizations may find it more helpful to focus on the continual improvement of their security culture, rather than finding a culprit for any security shortcomings. Similarly, Mayhew (2007, p. 145) emphasizes that overemphasizing the assignment of blame for any security failure can make employees more defensive, which can jeopardize efforts to improve security outcomes. This approach helped to gain insights into the challenges faced in implementing security policies, confirming the three themes identified from our literature review (including new employees, the initiative-taking approach, and the 'guilty-free' culture). It is necessary to discuss the conceptual contribution of these findings to the OHS literature and practical implications for security managers, and some limitations of our study and directions for future research. An occupational health and health management system is not effective unless accompanied by a positive safety culture in the workplace. The effectiveness could not be better demonstrated, as many organizations that introduced new occupational health and safety management strategies did not consider the impact of organizational culture on these strategies. Work in the 21st century has been characterized by expansions in the service and knowledge sectors, increases in the number of small businesses, unconventional work schedules, precarious workers, worker mobility, and older aged workers (Neira M. 2010, 2012).

These features have led to new and emerging issues in occupational health, including new work-related disorders, noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), and inequality in the availability of occupational health services (World Health Organization (WHO); Geneva (Switzerland) 2013). Of course, tackling these new and emerging problems also requires a culture of prevention at the national level.

The purpose of future studies will require:

- (1) how to change safety cultures in both theory and practice at the workplace level; and (“Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health Practice”)*
- (2) the role of a national prevention culture in dealing with new and emerging work-related health problems and traditional occupational diseases in the rapidly changing work environment.*

5. Its Effects on the Historical Development of Security Culture and Today

In 1993, the ACSNI Human Factors Working Group defined the safety culture and articulated the adequacy of an organization's health and safety management system. ("Safe & Healthy Workplace: Getting the Message to Workplace - DOSH") A safety culture has psychological, behavioral, and situational components. The psychological component consists of shared values, attitudes, perceptions and beliefs that guide safety decisions and behaviors (Health and Safety Executive (HSE) HSE Books; Suffolk (UK), 2005). ("Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety ... - Europe PMC") The behavioral component can be defined as the situational component as the methods related to safety in the workplace and the policies, procedures, regulations, organizational structures and management systems related to safety. The International Atomic Energy Agency has identified five characteristics of a positive safety culture. ("Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...")

- a. *First, leadership is a highly visible commitment. Collaboration and communication for safety with top management, which is a vital characteristic for maintaining a positive safety culture, is of paramount value.*
- b. *Second, security should be clearly communicated as a value, not a priority that can be traded in terms of cost and schedule.*
- c. *Third, decentralized decision-making and accountability of key security groups are important to creating and maintaining a positive safety culture.*
- d. *Fourth, all employees should learn about safety and contribute ideas about enhanced safety. A positive safety culture is achieved when employees learn from insight and intuition rather than events and change the way they think and act by sharing their experiences and addressing shared problems. ("Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...")*
- e. *Finally, a positive safety culture is one where safety is a top priority and integrated into every aspect of the company. ("Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...")*

Specifically, among the five attributes, employer leadership is key to fostering a positive safety culture. Single organizations have unique organizational cultures and safety cultures. Safety culture can be divided into five levels of development, among which are "pathological",

“reactive”, “calculating”, “proactive” and “productive”. In a “pathological” safety culture, employers and workers do not care about violating safety rules. (“Keynote address at the Saiosh 2019 Conference – Key-Worx”) This is often referred to as “the presence or absence of a safety culture” in the value of “maintenance”. In a “reactive” safety culture, safety only becomes important after an accident; this is often referred to as a “missing safety culture”. In a “calculatory” security culture, systems exist to manage all hazards; This is often referred to as a “planned safety culture” (Fleming M., 2001).

6. A “Initiative-taking” Safety Culture

In a “initiative-taking” safety culture, workers do not work on problems they find, but avoid problems in advance to improve the work environment. (“Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...”) A “productive” safety culture is a dynamic safety culture in which safety is embedded in the way we work and think. Thus, a poor or pathological safety culture can turn into a positive or productive safety culture when a change in the culture is effectively managed. (“Creating a Culture of Prevention in Occupational Safety and Health ...”) The human, social and economic costs of occupational accidents, injuries and diseases, and major industrial disasters have long been a source of concern at all levels, from the individual workplace to national and international. Measures and strategies designed to prevent, control, reduce or eliminate occupational hazards and risks have been continuously developed and implemented over the years to keep pace with technological and economic changes. (“Fundamental principles of ohs - SlideShare”) (“Black Sea Technical University”) Yet, despite sustained IF slow improvements, occupational accidents and diseases are still very frequent and their costs in terms of human suffering and economic burden remain significant. A recent ILO report estimates that 2 million occupational deaths occur worldwide each year (ILO, 2003b), with the highest rates of these deaths from work-related cancers, circulatory and cerebrovascular diseases, and some infectious diseases. The annual fatal and non-fatal occupational accident rate is estimated to be around 270 million (Hämäläinen, Takala, and Saarela, 2006).

About 160 million workers suffer from work-related illnesses, and about two-thirds of them are out of work for four working days or more as a result. (“УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ „ГОЦЕ ДЕЛЧЕВ“ ШТИП”) After work-related cancers, circulatory diseases and some infectious diseases, accidental occupational injuries are the fourth leading cause of work-related death. Recent data from the ILO and the World Health Organization (WHO) show that overall occupational accident and disease rates are slowly decreasing in most industrialized countries, but flat or increasing as countries develop and industrialize: (“Evaluation_of_Occupational_Health_Hazard.pdf - IOSR Journal...”)

In terms of European statistics, statistics on accidents at work (ESAW) per year in the 15 member states of the European Union (EU) prior to the enlargements in 2004 and 2007, approximately 5,000 workers were killed in workplace accidents and about 5 million workers were victims of accidents at work. they express (EU, 2004). Occupational death and accident rates in India and China are similar at 10.4 and 10.5 respectively at 100,000 for fatalities and 8,700 and 8,028 for accidents . In sub-Saharan Africa, the death rate per 100,000 workers is 21 and the accident rate is 16,000. This means that every year 54,000 workers die, and 42 million work-related accidents take place that take at least three days off work. About 30,000 deaths occur each year in Latin America and Black Pepper. The economic costs of these injuries and deaths are enormous at the business, national and global levels. If property losses from accidents and more specifically major industrial accidents are included, recent studies show that insured losses are around \$5 billion per year and are on the rise (Mitchell, 1996).

In addition, these figures are primarily based on acute and intense events and do not include uninsured losses, delayed losses associated with acute events such as oil and other toxic chemical spills, or environmental impact and losses caused by chronic industrial pollution. (“Module 1.pdf - Southern Luzon State University College of...”)

The total annual cost of work-related injuries and ill health in 2001 was estimated to be between €185 billion and €270 billion, or between 2.6 percent and 3.8 percent of the EU's GNP. By contrast, the cost of occupational accidents in Viet Nam for 2006 is estimated at \$3 billion (Viet Nam Government, 2006).

Safety culture and performance Safety culture is also difficult to measure by defining safety performance. Performance is often traditionally measured using self-reported and/or officially recorded accident statistics. However, this can be problematic: For example, because accidents

can be relatively rare events, they may not be recorded accurately or routinely, and risk exposure may not be considered. Ignorance provides fuel for accidents to happen. No matter how well defined a system is, someone will find a way to beat initiative-taking measures. There are many cases in the sector (Binz C, 2016.).

Many previous studies (Kao CS, Lai WH, Chuang TF, Lee JC. 2008) have indicated an important relationship between safety culture and safety communication. As a result, organizational culture, especially safety culture, is predicted to play a critical role in reducing safety communication, so hypotheses have been developed to explore the link between safety culture and safety communication. Safety culture has a positive effect on safety communication. The close context in which the individual performs his/her task is called the workplace environment. The environment in which employees work has a significant impact on the quality of their work and their performance. The wrong environment presents hazards, makes the workplace environment dangerous and slows down the worker's production rate (Rasool SF, Wang M, Tang M, Saeed A, Iqbal J., 2021). In addition, health and safety at work has professionals and legal obligations to provide a workplace that is free of hazards to workers that could result in significant physical injury or death . Because they should provide a safe and healthy working environment for their employees.

7. Perception of Corporate Occupational Health and Safety Culture

Institutionally, various and variable data are available to evaluate management support and performance in terms of occupational health and safety culture and communication of the team in safety culture, although the main topics are training and generally have the lowest averages. On the other hand, job satisfaction, which is the only area evaluated positively, is also presented in the others with the highest average (Carvalho REFL, 2017). This area can be a support for improving the safety culture, as a satisfied worker will be able to self-develop to improve attention, in line with management actions. A fit between management and staff should bring the desire of top management and what staff expect from the organization, not overlaps, but a common path towards a culture of safety (Amalberti R, Rocha R, Vilela RAG, 2018). In the analysis of the relationships between the two constructs, it should not be overlooked that most

of the presenters, except for job satisfaction and stress recognition dimensions, have low average values of safety, and that professionals have recognized stress factors even under adverse health conditions based on their work. Excluding job satisfaction and management perception both in the unit and in the hospital, safety and culture values for existing dimensions seem to tend to be evaluated more negatively than non-existent ones, according to occupational health knowledge and experience. The low perception of safety culture about managers is evidence observed not only locally but also nationally and internationally in studies (Sexton JB, Helmreich RL, Neilands TB, Rowan K, Vella K, Boyden J, et al., 2006).

8. Conclusion

Employee safety performances are affected by the company's safety culture. This study validates our assumptions that safety culture has a positive effect on safety performance through set-based safety communication. The results of this research add to the body of knowledge, not only in terms of the direct relationships between safety culture and safety communication, but also in terms of the indirect impact of safety culture and safety performance. This research, as a study that conceptualizes and empirically examines the mediating role of safety communication between safety culture and safety performance, is also of value in terms of its contribution to the Turkish literature. In addition, research on safety culture is limited, especially in Southeast Asian countries, including Turkey, apart from the United States and Europe. As this research provides strong guidelines that can be used by practitioners and academics, the findings also reveal that research is insufficient in terms of safety interventions and future studies. The findings have important implications for professionals. Previously, a positive safety culture was considered essential to maintaining workplace safety environments. However, the findings of our study suggest that increasing workplace safety organizations should focus on safety culture in addition to physical safety. (“Frontiers | Assessing the Mediating Role of Safety Communication ...”) Establishing an elevated level of safety culture at the management level is vital not only for psychosocial health but also for enhancing member safety performance. Establishing a work environment where employees and their management feel committed to their psychological well-being is directly proportional to the work demands and overloads, and in a psychosocially safe environment, it reduces employee accidents, deaths

as well as stresses, and more constructive inadequacy issues are allowed as needed. Security information, security procedures and the elements that will activate them are only possible with training. The security culture literature describes the practical steps that must be taken to implement a security culture in organizations. Among other effective practices, the safety culture in management performance evaluations and the assignment of people to senior roles based on their commitment to the safety culture policy should form other important sub-topics. Ultimately, our findings suggest that every organization, but especially high-risk organizations, should prioritize the mental health of workers, such as accidents and deaths, over their competitive needs (such as production) to positively impact their safety performance.

9. Resources

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